

Reconstitution of Brain Microsomal Calcium Channels and Olfactory Epithelium Cilia in Planar Bilayer Lipid Membrane Systems

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Two types of reconstitution experiments are described. One involves the study of single Ca^{2+} channels from rat brain microsomal membrane reconstituted at the tip of a patch clamp micropipette. The single channel conductance is found to be 80 and 125 ps in 50 mM Ca^{2+} . The open-time distribution follows a single exponential with a time constant (τ) of 7.34 ms. Further characterisation of this channel is in progress. We hypothesise this channel to be the same as that which is present in muscle sarcoplasmic reticulum. Also described are some of our methods to incorporate the olfactory epithelium cilia in planar bilayer systems so as to understand the 'odor to generator potential development' transduction process.

MEMBRANE reconstitution is the method of choice when one wants to unequivocally determine the function of a particular membrane component. One isolates, for example, a particular protein, reconstitutes it in a defined lipid milieu and studies its function. A large number of reconstitution studies have been carried out using both the planar bilayer lipid membranes (BLM) and the spherical liposome¹⁻⁵. Various membrane transport mechanisms have been characterised using this method. Planar BLMs have also been used for reconstituting various channel-forming substances and studying single channel activity^{6,7}. Membrane reconstitution remains probably the only method to study the function of the membrane proteins present in the organelle membranes.

In this paper we limit ourselves to two reconstituted systems which are being studied in our laboratory. One is the reconstitution of the brain microsomal Ca^{2+} channel in a BLM formed at the tip of a patch-clamp micropipette to study this channel's activity using the patch-clamp technique. The other is the reconstitutions of olfactory epithelium cilia using planar BLMs.

Experimental

Brain microsomal Ca^{2+} channels: The introduction and improvement of the patch-clamp technique⁸ has revolutionised the study of ionic channels in native membranes. A whole host of parameters, such as channel conductance, selectivity to various ions, probability of mean open time (P_o) and its dependence on voltage, pH, etc., and mean open time constants and their modulation by various pharmacologic agents, can be determined using the patch-clamp technique.

Using the patch-clamp technique, it is possible to make patches from the membranes which are accessible, such as the peripheral plasma membranes. Intracellular organelle membranes cannot be as easily studied by the patch-clamp technique. So, one way of studying the channels present in cytoplasmic membranes is to isolate the internal organelle membrane of interest as vesicles and study them using the old bilayer reconstitution method by controlled fusion of one or a few vesicles with the BLM, if one wants to study microscopic channel activity^{9,10}. There have also been a few attempts to make large vesicles by repeatedly freezing and thawing small vesicles and taking a patch out of this large vesicle¹¹.

Recently, it has been shown that it is possible to make lipid bilayers at the tip of glass microelectrodes¹⁰⁻¹⁴. And it was shown as early as 1976¹⁵ that it is possible to disperse insoluble biological membrane material in excess of exogenous lipid by sonication. This dispersed material can be lyophilised and dissolved in decane to make regular planar BLMs. By this method one can reconstitute and study the particular protein of interest. It has also been shown that the lyophilised material can be dissolved in readily evaporable solvents such as pentane or hexane, and the solution can be used to make monolayers; two monolayers can be brought together to oppose each other and to form a bilayer¹⁶. In these reconstitution methods, some of the proteins do remain intact and hence can be studied. In our laboratory we have combined the above two methods and have attempted to study the brain microsomal Ca^{2+} channel¹⁷.

Preparation of brain microsomal membranes: The microsomal membranes were prepared and

characterised as reported earlier^{19,20}. Fresh rat or bovine forebrains were homogenised in a teflon glass homogeniser in 0.32 M ice-cold sucrose, 2 mM HEPES (pH 7.6) (10% homogenate). The homogenate was spun at 12000 g and the pellet discarded. The supernatant was again spun at 12000 g for 30 min. Then the supernatant was spun at 100000 g for 90 min. The pellet was the microsomal fraction. For further sub-fractionation it was layered over a discontinuous sucrose density gradient of 2, 1.3, 1 and 0.8 M, and centrifuged at 85000 g for 16 h in a Beckman SW 27 rotor. The bands at the interfaces were carefully collected and centrifuged at 100000 g for 90 min to collect the microsomes. The marker enzyme activities were determined^{19,20} to confirm an enriched microsomal preparation.

Dispersion of the microsomal fraction in excess lipid²¹: Asolectin was added to a sample of microsomal membranes in distilled water to produce a final asolectin to protein ratio of 10 : 1 (w/w); the volume was adjusted so that the final asolectin concentration was 1–2% (w/v). The mixture was sonicated under N₂ at 0° in a Branson sonifier at maximum setting for 10 min, lyophilised and stored desiccated at –80°. The asolectin, a crude mixture of soybean phospholipids, was treated with acetone and ether according to the reported method²¹.

Formation of monolayers and bilayers: The lyophilised brain microsomal preparation was suspended in n-pentane or n-hexane at a concentration of 10 mg ml⁻¹. Five microliters (μl) of this solution was spread on a 35 mm plastic petri dish filled with the buffer solution pH 7.4 containing appropriate amount of Ca²⁺. The bilayers were made at the tips of patch-clamp micropipettes^{10–14}. The tips of the micropipettes (< 5 μm dia) were fire-polished.

Single channel recording, storage and data analysis: Single channel currents were measured by the current-to-voltage converter of a Dagan 8800 total clamp system. The feedback resistor of the current-to-voltage converter had a resistance of 10 GΩ. Thus, our system had the sensitivity of 10 mV per 1 pA. The patch-clamp electrode was partially filled with the test solution and pushed into the electrode holder which contained a chloridised silver wire. The electrode holder was connected to the inverting input of the current to voltage converter op. amp. A reference electrode was immersed in the solution of the petri dish. Command voltages were applied to the Ag/AgCl electrode in the pipette by applying the voltage to the non-inverting input of the current-to-voltage converter. Single channel current traces were recorded on video tapes by using a Hitachi VCR connected to Neurocorder DR-484.

The data were analysed by acquiring them off-line from the tape to a HP Vectra ES/2 and storing them on a disk. The data were acquired either through a window/event detector or in the through-pot mode (in which a complete stretch of data of about 40 s of tape playing time in the EP mode is

acquired). The data were stored in files, and (i) the mean open time, (ii) the open time distributions, (iii) the closed time distributions and (iv) the amplitude distribution can be analysed by using different computer programs. Various statistical analyses were performed. Hard copies of single channel recordings or open time histograms or amplitude histograms were obtained by an HPH 7470 plotter connected to the computer.

Olfactory epithelium :

There are essentially four configurations of BLM settings: (i) regular two open wells, (ii) one hydrostatically closed chamber, (iii) stabilisation using a sieve or polymerisation and (iv) BLM on the tip of a micropipette. Each of the four configurations had pros and cons. The regular BLM had the advantage of two open chambers in which the solutions can be replaced (or at least compounds can be added); the major disadvantage being the fragility of the BLM. The second setup had the advantage of relative stability and ease of handling but had one closed compartment. The third configuration²² was a collection of small diameter BLMs. The fourth configuration is essentially a patch-clamp setup. The major advantage of it is the resolution (few pA) and thus the ability to measure single channel activity. Single channel activity was recorded by using the other two methods as well.

Regular BLM is usually formed in a hole in the wall of a cup made from a highly hydrophobic material such as teflon. The diameter of the hole was 2 mm or less. The cup was held in a plexiglass structure providing a second chamber, a viewing path and a mechanical support for the teflon cup. The electrical connections were made to the solutions in the chambers by saturated calomel electrodes (SCE). The formation of the BLM in the opening was a spontaneous process. Spreading of an adequate forming solution progressed by a spontaneous thinning process to form a BLM. Sometimes the process needed to be initiated by applying potential for a short time. The commonly used forming solutions were 1% lecithin in n-decane, 4% oxidised cholesterol in n-octane, 1% glycerol mono-oleate (GMO) or glycerol di-oleate (GDO) in squalene; the BLMs formed from these solutions being called 'solvent-free'. They normally have a specific capacitance of C_m = 0.78 μF cm⁻².

Hydrostatically stabilised BLM was used by many investigators. The bilayer is created by passing a hydrostatically closed chamber through a monolayer created on the surface of the bathing solution. The surface is an interface between the aqueous solution and the air and thus allows for the spreading of forming solution to a monolayer. The hole has to be treated first with petroleum gel or squalene in order to provide the necessary Plateau-Gibbs border².

Isolation of olfactory cilia was done from frog olfactory epithelium. Following Chen and Lancet²³

we used the calcium pulse and 10% ethanol method as described by Linck³⁴. The frogs were pithed and decapitated. The olfactory epithelium was dissected and deciliated. The epithelium was placed at roughly 10 times its volume in ice-cold 0.1 mM EDTA and washed twice by replacing the EDTA solution. Each 10 g epithelium was suspended to 100 ml 10% ethanol, 0.1 M NaCl, 2 mM EDTA and 30 mM Tris pH 8.0 at room temperature. The epithelium was allowed to equilibrate for 2 min while stirring. A 1 M CaCl₂ solution was added rapidly to make a 10 mM CaCl₂ solution. At room temperature the peak deciliation was about 4 min; at 0° it is twice the time. The suspension was filtered through cheese cloth and centrifuged at 1500 g for 5 min. The supernatant was centrifuged at 10000 g for 5 min, and the pellet, which being essentially pure cilia, was resuspended in the appropriate buffer (based on MOPS buffer pH 7.4). The suspension was then sonicated to form vesicles. The detection of the vesicles was done by light microscope. In order to make preparation for patch clamp experiments, the suspension was lyophilised instead of sonicated.

In regular BLM and hydrostatically stabilised BLM the vesicles created were fused to the layer by adding CaCl₂ and then KCl. Once the channels' conductance change was observed, the chamber was perfused by 200 mM potassium acetate/0.5 mM EGTA/5 mM HEPES pH 7.0 to prevent further incorporation and to eliminate the salt gradient³⁵.

The general protocol of the experiments was (i) isolation of the cilia or getting the lyophilised material into a BLM forming solution, (ii) creating a BLM, (iii) incorporating the proteins into the BLM, (iv) measuring the control conductances/channel kinetics, and (v) introducing the perturbation.

The measurements of the conductance were under voltage clamp configuration, thereby monitoring the current under a determined voltage. In a situation with many channels and many ions, the total conductance was measured in the form of an I-V relationship curve. In the case of a single channel both the I-V curve and the kinetics of opening were measured.

Results and Discussion

Brain microsomal Ca²⁺ channels: In an earlier work on bovine brain microsomal channel done by Vassilev *et al.*¹⁶, it was found that the channel conductance was about 107 ps with 50 mM Ca²⁺ as the charge carrier. In 50 mM Ba²⁺ the conductance was 38 ps. One μ M ruthenium red strongly inhibited Ca²⁺ channel activity. Channel activity was stimulated by nucleotides and inositol 1,4,5-triphosphate. Na⁺ added asymmetrically to the membrane bilayer induced an increase in Ca²⁺ channel activity.

Some of our recent work on rat brain microsomal Ca²⁺ channels¹⁷ shows that in symmetrical 50 mM

Ca²⁺ solution, the channel openings can be seen (Fig. 1) and the amplitude is distributed in a bimodal fashion with one peak at $g \approx 80$ ps and the other peak at $g \approx 125$ ps (Fig. 2). The open time distributions (Fig. 3) can be fitted to a single exponential with $\tau = 7.34$ ms.

Further characterisations of this channel are in progress and our main objectives in the near future are as follows. (i) Study the characteristics of a brain microsomal Ca²⁺ release channel: (a) study the selectivity of this channel to monovalent and divalent cations, (b) study the conductance of this channel as a function of cation concentration (mainly Ca²⁺ concentration), (c) study the open state probability (P_o) of this channel at varying pH, (d) study the open state probability (P_o) of the channel as a function of pCa, and (e) study the

Fig. 1. Typical Ca²⁺ channel activity with 50 mM Ca²⁺ as the charge carrier. Symmetrical solutions both in the pipette and the bath. The command voltage is 90 mV.

Fig. 2. Amplitude histogram of the channel activity in 50 mM symmetrical Ca²⁺ solution. The command voltage is 90 mV. The bimodal distribution can be seen.

Fig. 3. Open time histogram. The data can be fitted to a single exponential with a τ of 7.34 ms.

open state probability of the channel as a function of various holding potentials. (ii) Study the effect of various intracellular 2nd messengers and nucleotides on the activity of this channel: (a) study the effect of $\text{Ins}-\text{P}_3$ on the open state probability and the open time constants of this channel, (b) study the effect of GTP on the open state probability and open time constants of this channel, and (c) study the effect of cAMP on the open state probability and open time constants of this channel. (iii) Study the effect of ryanodine and heptanol and octanol on the open state probability of this channel. (iv) Study to identify whether this channel has various subconducting states (as in SR Ca^{2+} channel) and, if so, which subconductance state/states is/are more common. (v) Attempt to purify the microsomal Ca^{2+} channel to homogeneity and to determine the molecular weight of the channel protein by running SDS-Polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis. (vi) Reconstitute the purified Ca^{2+} channel protein in bilayer lipid membrane and see if one can get back channel activity. (vii) Make electron microscopic studies of the purified channel protein.

Olfactory epithelium reconstitution: Any sensory system must have mapping of the property of the stimulus to some map in the CNS. These maps are established for all the senses except taste and olfaction. The primary reason for the difficulty in establishing the representation of olfactory stimulus to the CNS arises from the lack of knowledge of the parameters of the stimulus. Where in the visual system the space of the stimulus is continuous in both spatial and spectra, and the touch is continuous in spatial and intensity, the continuous properties of the olfactory stimulus are not known. Furthermore, it is not known if there is a continuum, as the stimulus is a discrete event of molecular recognition²². The first step in identifying these parameters

is to identify the primary events of the transduction. Studies using reconstituted systems aim at these events in a system without cell heterogeneity and prereceptor factors²⁶.

In order to understand the building blocks of the transduction we take the approach of controlling a maximum of variables in the system. Reconstitution of the part of the system that is responsible for the detection and transduction²⁴⁻³⁰ can provide almost total control of the environment. The relative ease of controlling the environment is important in experiments that are directed at the prominent parameters that are significant in an odorant.

This project can be viewed as a pilot study for reconstitution of purified proteins and later genetically engineered proteins. In the case of purified proteins the natural membrane does not exist. The results obtained from a system like that cannot readily be extrapolated to the natural system. Thus the reconstituted system serves as an important intermediate reference.

The BLM method has been used since the 1960s to provide a model system for a biological membrane. It has been used for the study of the physical properties of the membrane as well as for reconstitution of membrane systems². A reconstitution experiment involves few stages: (i) isolation of the membrane systems, (ii) creation of a BLM, (iii) incorporation of the natural membrane preparation into the BLM, and (iv) measurements and perturbations. The methods isolation of olfactory epithelial cilia^{29,30,32,34} and the methods for creating BLM^{2,10,12,16} have been described by many authors.

Reconstitution of olfactory epithelium has been done by few investigators. Both DC changes³¹ and single channel openings^{32,35} were observed. Using solvent-containing BLM and with a fraction of olfactory epithelium, a DC change was induced by a camphor solution³¹. Using an essentially solvent-free BLM, with the addition of olfactory epithelial homogenate, a single K^+ channel was observed. Addition of diethyl sulphide caused an increase in the open state probability. Reconstitution of epithelial homogenate eliminates the variability of receptor sensitivity due to spatial organisation. The reconstituted system is suitable to provide answers for mechanisms which do not depend on the mucous layer^{37,42} but rather on the binding sites for the odorants³⁸.

We are equipped to perform two types of reconstitution experiments: (i) incorporation into planar BLM and (ii) reconstitution on the tip of a micropipette^{18,33}. Thus, we can study the DC properties of a reconstituted system as well as the high resolution study of ionic channels. As mentioned above, the general aim of these studies is at factors which influence the generator potentials. Few questions can be answered by studying a reconstituted system. The first question is: what effects do the different

odorants have on the different ionic currents? This question can be expanded to the interdependence of the changes induced by different odorants³⁶. Thus, by studying changes in the conductance of ionic current in response to a family of odorants and odorant mixtures, one can learn on the receptor itself. There are two resolutions in which the system can be studied: (i) DC conductance change for a particular ion and (ii) the effect of an odorant on single channel kinetics. The second set of questions examines the effects of one odorant on different ion conductances, i.e. what relative changes in the conductances of the different ions occur in response to a single odorant? This study cannot be performed at the level of a single channel and cannot be performed *in vivo*. This study requires a one cation environment with a setup in which the solutions can be replaced.

A third topic is based on the observation of Pace *et al.*³⁰ and followed by others³²⁻³⁵. The effects of cyclic nucleotides on the conductance of cation is described by Nakamura and Gold³⁹. This is only one example of a second messenger system and Winegar *et al.*⁴⁰ suggested calcium and calmodulin involvement. Calcium is also shown to have an influence on potassium conductance by Labarca *et al.*³⁵. Burch and Huque⁴¹ reported on odorant simulated phosphoinositide turnover. In this study we want to address the question: does the response to odorant depend on the existing level of second messenger in the cell⁴? A second question is: which conductances change directly by the various second messenger systems? In this context it is important to assay the production of cAMP and IP₃ from relatively intact membranes.

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